

Semiempirical AM1 investigation of geometric and electronic effects in Myers' cyclization reaction

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Semiempirical quantum chemical AM1 methodology has been employed to find out various geometric and electronic effects in Myers' cyclization reaction. Reasonable trends in the activation barriers with the variation in the distance between the reactive sites are obtained. The proximity criterion is operative in allene-ene-yne cyclizations too, but the effect is less than in corresponding Bergman cyclizations. The computed results have been interpreted on the basis of the geometric features contributing to the overall activation enthalpies.

In the recent years extensive research effort has been directed towards molecules which selectively bind to DNA and cleave it. While significant progress has been made in the isolation and evaluation of naturally occurring DNA cleaving agents¹, a major area of research activity is in the design and synthesis of new compounds which can recognize specific sequence of DNA and cut the strands. A variant of the Bergman cyclization² reaction has been reported by Myers (Scheme 1)³. The reaction involves the cyclization of (Z)-hepta-1,2,4-trien-6-yne (**1**) to yield a 1,4-biradical intermediate $\alpha,3$ -didehydrotoluene (**2**). Interestingly, the naturally occurring antitumor antibiotic neocarzinostatin⁴ has been suggested to cleave DNA by generating a biradical intermediate following Myers' cyclization. An understanding of the factors controlling the ease of this cyclization reaction is therefore as important as for the Bergman cyclization.

Scheme 1. Myers' cyclization reaction

Structural and electronic factors in Myers' cyclization have not been studied in sufficient detail so far. Therefore a critical evaluation of the cyclization of the allene-ene-yne moiety is called for. Here we report the results of MO calculations of this reaction in some representative monocyclic systems. We specifically examine the relative importance of the π -bond proximity effect for Myers' cyclization reaction. On the basis of experimental and MM2 studies of various model monocyclic enediynes, Nicolaou *et al.*⁵ proposed that the ease of Bergman cycliza-

tion depends on the distance between the two terminal carbon atoms of the reacting π -bonds. MO calculations confirm the general validity of this proposal^{3,6}. It would be of interest to evaluate the proximity criterion for Myers' cyclization, in view of its mechanistic similarity to Bergman cyclization as well as for potential application in the design of additional systems for DNA cleavage. Here we have carried out a theoretical study of this aspect of Myers' cyclization reaction.

First, cyclization of the parent allene-ene-yne systems (Z)-hepta-1,2,4-trien-6-yne (**1**) was studied as the basic reference system. Next, three model compounds, **3**, **4**, and **5** (Scheme 2) were studied in which the distance ($R_{\pi\pi}$) between the cyclization centres are varied by connecting the triple bond and the allene unit of **1** with an appropriate saturated $-(CH_2)_n$ - bridge.

Computational details :

It was shown that the performance of AM1⁷ methodology is quite satisfactory for Bergman cyclization profiles in ene-diyne systems, particularly to reproduce the diminished barriers with short in-plane π -bond distances⁸. Therefore, we have employed the same methodology to optimize the geometry at the AM1/RHF level followed by single point calculations on key stationary points at the PECl = 8 (Pair Excitation Configuration Interaction) level, in the present study. The energy profiles of all the systems, **1**, **3**, **4** and **5** are determined considering the newly formed C-C bond distance as the reaction coordinate. The transition states and intermediates have been characterized in conventional ways. To get an idea about the extent of bond formation at various stationary points, the distance between the terminal carbon atoms of the two reacting π -bonds at reactant, transition state and product are shown in Table 1.

The heats of formation of reactant, transition state and product, calculated at AMI/RHF and AMI/PECI = 8 level are shown in Table 2. The computed activation enthalpies and heats of reactions are summarized in Table 3.

Table 1. AMI computed distance (Å) between the carbon atoms forming the new σ -bond in the reactants (R_{gs}), transition states (R_{ts}) and the products (R_p) for Myers' cyclization

Enyne-allene	R_{gs}	R_{ts}	R_p
1	3.56	1.88	1.47
5	3.21	1.87	1.48
4	3.12	1.90	1.48
3	2.79	1.87	1.50

Table 2. AMI heats of formation (kcal mol⁻¹) of the reactants, transition states and the 1,4-biradical products of Myers' cyclization

Enyne-allene	ΔH_f^\ddagger (Reactant)		ΔH_f^\ddagger (T.S.)		ΔH_f^\ddagger (Product)	
	RHF	PECI = 8	RHF	PECI = 8	RHF	PECI = 8
1	114.1	104.9	152.9	144.1	121.4	112.6
5	109.5	106.0	149.8	141.5	118.3	112.3
4	97.3	91.2	135.2	127.7	104.5	95.2
3	110.1	103.7	142.6	134.6	121.6	111.2

Table 3. AMI enthalpies of activation and heats of reaction for Myers' cyclization as well as the distance between the carbon atoms forming the new σ -bond in the reactants (R_{gs})

Enyne-allene	R_{gs} Å	Enthalpies of activation kcal mol ⁻¹		Heats of reactions kcal mol ⁻¹	
		RHF	PECI = 8	RHF	PECI = 8
1	3.56	38.5	39.2	7.3	7.7
5	3.21	40.3	35.5	8.8	6.3
4	3.12	37.9	36.5	7.2	4.0
3	2.79	32.5	30.9	11.5	7.5

Results and Discussion

The AMI/RHF computed energy profile for Myers' cyclization of the prototype acyclic enyne-allene (*Z*)-hepta-1,2,4-trien-6-yne (**1**) corresponds to one-step process, consistent with the previous *ab initio* study by Koga and Morokuma⁹. In the AMI/RHF transition structure the newly formed C–C bond length is computed to be 1.88 Å (Table 1), slightly shorter than the value of 1.96 Å at CASSCF4/MIDI level⁹. Interestingly, the key C=CH₂ bond length of the allene unit is found to be 1.32 Å at AMI level, suggesting retention of considerable π -bond character of that bond in the transition state. Moreover, the exocyclic methylene is calculated to be only partially twisted, by around 50°. These results indicate that there is considerable π -conjugation between the allenic methylene and the aromatic ring in the transition state. In the previous study at CASSCF4/MIDI level⁹, the C=CH₂ bond length was found to be 1.37 Å. However, in contrast to AMI/RHF results, the exocyclic methylene was computed to be almost perpendicular to the aromatic ring, indicating ineffi-

cient conjugation at the transition state. The remaining geometric parameters obtained at the AMI and *ab initio* level are similar. The bending angle of the C–C–C framework of allene unit in the AMI computed transition state is found to be 141.5°, close to the value of 140.8° at CASSCF4/MIDI level⁹. The length of the newly formed C–C bond (1.88 Å) at the transition state of Myers' cyclization is significantly longer than that computed for Bergman cyclization of enediyne⁸. This suggests that although the transition state structures are generally product-like for both reactions, it is less so for Myers' cyclization.

The AMI/RHF heat of formation of the transition state resulting from **1** is 152.6 kcal mol⁻¹ (Table 2). The value reduces to 144.1 kcal mol⁻¹ on inclusion of CI (PECI = 8). Although the transition state is expected to be diradicaloid in character, the reduction in energy on inclusion of CI is only marginal. The same trend in energy at RHF and PECI = 8 levels is found in the case of the corresponding biradical products also (Table 2). The AMI/RHF enthalpy of activation for Myers' cyclization of (*Z*)-hepta-1,2,4-trien-6-yne (**1**) is 38.5 kcal mol⁻¹ (Table 3). Experimentally the activation barrier is estimated¹⁰ to be 21–23 kcal mol⁻¹, substantially lower than the AMI computed value. The previously reported *ab initio* CASSCF calculation with a large MIDI4 basis set also yields a relatively large activation barrier⁹ of 33.3 kcal mol⁻¹, quite comparable to the AMI/RHF value. The AMI/RHF level also predicts that the reaction is endothermic by a modest amount (Table 3). The AMI/PECI = 8 computed value is similar, 7.7 kcal mol⁻¹ (Table 3).

The AMI/RHF computed energy profiles for Myers' cyclization of **3–5** are found to be similar in nature to that of **1**. The reaction is a single-step process for all the substrates. Although the calculated distance between the carbon atoms forming the new C–C σ -bond in the reactant geometry is computed to vary over a fairly wide range, from 3.56 to 2.79 Å, the newly formed C–C bond distance (R_{ts}) in the transition state is almost constant, 1.87–1.90 Å (Table 1). Similarly, the C–C distance (R_p) in the diradical products vary within the range 1.47–1.50 Å (Table 1). On going from the acyclic allene-ene-yne **1** to the 10-membered system **5**, the distance between two reactive sites decreases by 0.35 Å (Table 1). The reduction in the corresponding activation enthalpy is marginal, 3.7 kcal mol⁻¹ (Table 3). Further reduction in the distance between the atoms forming the new C–C σ -bond on going from **5** to **3**, results in additional lowering of the activation barrier (Table 3). Overall, the proximity effect on the computed barriers is not as dramatic as noted for Bergman cyclization⁸.

The lower sensitivity of the proximity effect on activation barriers in Myers' cyclization compared to Bergman process can be traced to the different electronic and geometric factors of the reactants and transition states in these reactions. As the two in-plane π -bonds are brought closer by enclosing the enediyne moiety in a ring, the strong four-electron destabilization is significant in the reactant geometry itself. As a result, the activation barrier for Bergman cyclization decreases remarkably^{5,8,11}. On the other hand, the corresponding interaction is not equally significant for Myers' cyclization. The AMI/RHF optimized ground state geometries of all the reactants reveal that the two reacting π -bonds of $C_3=C_2$ and $C_6=C_7$ (Scheme 2) are not coplanar, but nearly orthogonal to each other. Hence, the ground state destabilization due to close shell electron

Scheme 2. Myers' cyclization reactions of 3, 4 and 5

repulsion is relatively small and the reduction in activation barrier is not as large as in the case of Bergman cyclization.

Another factor determining the activation barrier of Myers' cyclization is the twist of the allenic methylene unit at the transition state. In the ground state, the allene unit would prefer its characteristic orthogonal arrangement of the cumulative π -bonds. On the other hand, planarity would be favored in the product biradical in view of benzylic conjugation. The transition structure is computed to have an intermediate twist for all the allene-ene-yne substrates at the AMI level (Table 4). This distortion would make a significant contribution to the overall activation enthalpy for Myers' cyclization. Evidently, this geometric feature has no counterpart in Bergman cyclization.

Table 4. AMI computed angle of twist (degree) of the allenic methylene unit (numbering according to Scheme 2) at the reactant and the transition state

Reactant	Twist angle in reactant		Twist angle in T.S.	
	$H_4C_1C_3H_6$	$C_6C_1C_3H_6$	$H_4C_1C_2C_7$	$C_6C_1C_2C_7$
5	86	-96	-124	52
4	86	-96	-140	33
3	84	-100	-150	20

Conclusions : Analysis of AMI computed geometries of 3, 4 and 5 reveals a near-optimal orthogonal geometry of the allenic methylene unit with respect to the adjacent π -bond. The twist angles in the transition states for the various substrates are also comparable, although not identical (Scheme 2, Table 4). Thus, the increase in energy due to twisting of the allenic unit is a common factor in all the substrates. Hence, reduction in the distance between the cyclization centres alone does not result in large lowering of the activation barrier for Myers' cyclization.

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